

CORONARY HEART DISEASE: CAUSES, SYMPTOMS AND TREATMENT METHODS

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Abstract: This paper discusses the pathogenesis, clinical manifestations and relationship of coronary heart disease, causes, symptoms and treatment methods, as well as modern approaches to the prevention and treatment of this disease. Coronary heart disease is the leading cause of death worldwide. The pathogenesis of the disease is based on the discrepancy between the heart muscle's need for oxygen and the ability to deliver it through the coronary arteries. The main cause is vascular atherosclerosis.

Key words: coronary heart disease, atherosclerosis, angina, myocardial infarction, coronary circulation, cardiosclerosis, heart failure, coronary angiography.

INTRODUCTION

The heart is supplied with oxygen and nutrients through the coronary arteries. If, due to atherosclerotic deposits in the vessels, the blood flow volume is reduced, the heart begins to "suffocate", a pathological condition develops - coronary heart disease. It is one of the most common cardiac diseases worldwide and can lead to other serious conditions such as heart muscle weakness or heart attack.

Coronary heart disease is a chronic disease associated with impaired blood supply to the myocardium as a result of atherosclerotic lesions of the coronary arteries. The article discusses the main causes of coronary heart disease, clinical manifestations, modern methods of diagnosis and therapy, as well as preventive

measures.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Symptoms and risk factors

The main symptom of coronary heart disease is chest pain (angina). In addition to hereditary factors and diabetes, risk factors include smoking, high blood pressure, high blood lipids and obesity.

Causes and risk factors: atherosclerosis (narrowing of the lumen of the coronary arteries), arterial hypertension, high cholesterol (dyslipidemia), smoking, diabetes, excess weight and a sedentary lifestyle, psychoemotional stress, hereditary predisposition.

Clinical symptoms:

- Pain or discomfort behind the breastbone (pressing, burning);
- Pain radiating to the left arm, neck, lower jaw;
- Shortness of breath during exertion;
- Fatigue, sweating, dizziness;
- In case of a heart attack - intense pain that is not relieved by nitroglycerin.

Classification of ischemic heart disease (according to WHO):

1. Sudden coronary death (primary cardiac arrest)
2. Angina:
 - Stable (FC I-IV)
 - Unstable
3. Myocardial infarction (with and without ST segment elevation)
4. Postinfarction cardiosclerosis
5. Painless forms of ischemia

Diagnosis

In some cases, a description of symptoms is enough to diagnose "ischemic heart disease". However, as a rule, special diagnostics are required, including various studies. They allow you to assess the function of the heart and coronary arteries and may include:

- Resting ECG;
- Exercise ECG;
- Heart ultrasound (echocardiography).

If necessary, additional examinations may be prescribed, such as stress echocardiography, MRI or CT scan of the heart. If there are certain indications, cardiac catheterization is performed.

Basic diagnostics: ECG (at rest and with stress); EchoCG (echocardiography); bicycle ergometry, stress test; coronary angiography (gold standard); blood tests (troponins, lipid profile, glucose).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Treatment of coronary heart disease

The goal of therapy for coronary heart disease is to expand narrowed coronary vessels. This should improve blood flow and supply to the heart muscle. The main component of treatment for coronary heart disease is drug therapy, which is aimed, on the one hand, at pathologies that are risk factors, and on the other hand, at improving blood flow to the heart. Taking anticoagulant drugs, especially aspirin, is a preventive measure to prevent a heart attack.

However, if modern drugs for coronary heart disease (anticoagulants, beta-blockers, cholesterol-lowering drugs, nitrates) no longer provide the necessary effect, vascular narrowing must be eliminated using a special intervention.

The main method of restoring blood flow is catheter intervention, including angioplasty with stenting.

Under certain circumstances, catheter manipulation is performed to restore blood flow - angioplasty with stenting. The placement of a stent (a metal tube-shaped implant) in a coronary artery supports it from the inside and prevents it from closing again.

In particularly severe cases, surgery (bypass surgery) may be required to treat coronary artery disease. The narrowed coronary vessels are replaced with the patient's own healthy vessels, and the heart begins to receive enough oxygen again.

The variety of diagnostic procedures and treatment options offered by modern medicine for the treatment of coronary artery disease explains the importance of additional consultations for this disease.

Drug treatment:

- antianginal drugs (nitrates, beta-blockers, calcium antagonists);
- antithrombotic therapy (aspirin, clopidogrel);
- statins (lowering cholesterol);
- ACE inhibitors or ARBs (for hypertension and reduced ejection fraction);
- hypoglycemic therapy (for diabetes).

Invasive methods:

- percutaneous coronary intervention (stenting);
- coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG).

Complications:

- 1) myocardial infarction;
- 2) heart failure;
- 3) heart rhythm disturbances;
- 4) sudden cardiac death.

Prevention: smoking cessation; weight control; diet low in saturated fats; regular physical activity; blood pressure and blood sugar control; taking statins and antiplatelet agents if necessary.

Coronary heart disease is a condition characterized by the narrowing or blockage of coronary arteries due to the buildup of plaque. This can lead to reduced blood flow to the heart muscle, ultimately causing chest pain (angina), shortness of breath, heart attacks, and other serious complications.

Coronary heart disease is a condition in which, the coronary circulation system fails to supply the cardiac muscle with a sufficient amount of blood. The insufficient circulation of blood to the heart also results in the deterioration of the surrounding tissue. It is a common ailment that has been identified as the primary cause for premature death across the continents. Although the condition is commonly equated with an artery disease that is atherosclerotic in nature, it can also be triggered due to coronary vasospasm and subsequently, stenosis. In this condition, the heart is deprived of the required amount of blood and oxygen. The surrounding tissue is affected on account of the narrowing of the blood vessels. If left untreated, it results in death.

CONCLUSION

The heart pumps oxygenated blood that is received from the lungs to various parts of the body. The oxygen-rich blood is pumped out via coronary arteries. In the case of coronary heart disease, the heart's blood supply is interrupted and reduced on an account of a lining within the artery walls, of fatty substances. Subsequent atherosclerosis results in frequent angina and even myocardial infarction.

Coronary heart disease is a socially significant disease that requires an integrated approach to treatment and prevention. Early diagnosis, timely drug and surgical therapy significantly improve the prognosis and quality of life of patients.

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